

Effects of cadmium on *SIRE1* retrotransposon polymorphism in wheat genome

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Transposable elements (TEs) reflect the plasticity and evolution of genomes throughout the tree of life and represent a large part of the repetitive sequences of plant genomes as well as the resulting diversity. The activity of retrotransposons, which lead to epigenetic changes as a result of the influence of various abiotic stress factors, and the determination of their polymorphism ratios form the basis of this research work. For this purpose, the *SIRE1* retrotransposon specific to the soybean plant was determined by the *IRAP* marker method in callus and leaf samples of wheat plants subjected to CdSO₄ stress. In contrast to the callus samples, bands were identified in the 750–1750 bp range in the leaf samples. While no polymorphism was detected in the callus, a polymorphism rate of 0-20% was calculated in leaf samples. Based on the results of the research, the determination of soybean-specific retrotransposons in wheat can be explained by the possibility of horizontal gene transfer.

Keywords: Epigenetics, retrotransposon, *IRAP* marker, CdSO₄, callus, Horizontal transfers

INTRODUCTION

Retrotransposons are elements (TEs) that increase the copy number by converting the transcribed RNA genome into cDNA, which then integrates or transposes into the genome. Recently, the sequencing and annotation of a growing number of plant genomes have made it clear that they are composed not only of genes directing metabolism, environmental response, and morphogenesis but also of transposable elements (TEs). TE families with thousands of members make up 80% or more of the total DNA of large genomes such as barley, wheat, and maize (Schulman, 2013). Despite the occasional introduction of selectively beneficial TE as a result of epigenetic effects, the vast majority of TE activity is likely to be selective or neutral at best and lethal at worst (Charles et al., 2004; Brookfield, 2005). This is largely achieved by epigenetic silencing of autonomous elements. This process involves small RNAs, DNA methylation, and various histone modifications (Lisch 2009; Slotkin et al., 2007). However, there are exceptions where epigenetic regulation of a transposable element can have dramatic effects on gene expression. Retrotransposons are divided into two main classes based on the presence or absence of long terminal repeats (LTR and non-LTR retrotransposons). Transposable elements can disrupt a gene coding

sequence, have an effect on splicing, or an insertion, promoter/enhancer region, and most importantly gene expression. In addition, promoters within TE can initiate transcription of neighboring genes while spreading to adjacent chromatin, leading to epigenetic changes. Although often viewed and studied as molecular parasites, retrotransposons have been found to influence neighboring gene expression and play a structural and potential regulatory role at the centromere. Plants are an excellent system for studying the mechanisms of DNA methylation and small RNA-mediated inhibition of LTR retrotransposons of retrotransposon transcripts. However, the analysis of multicopy mobile elements is much more difficult than the analysis of single-copy genes located in fixed regions of the genome (Defraia et al., 2014; Cho, 2021).

Plants are constantly exposed to a wide range of environmental stresses that reduce and limit productivity (Verma et al., 2013). Radiation, salinity, floods, drought, global climate, heavy metals, etc. Abiotic stress factors such as drought are causing the loss of major crop products worldwide. Stresses, altered gene expression, cell metabolism, and changes in growth rate ultimately affect fertility and other important processes. As a result of these processes, traits that lead to epigenetic changes in the plant organism and can be transmitted to several generations are obtained

(Gull et al., 2019). Cadmium (Cd) is among the most toxic and harmful heavy metals for all living organisms in the world. This metal is found everywhere in the environment, including soil, water, and air (Jibril et al., 2017; Raza et al., 2020a). In addition to affecting the growth of plants, soil contamination with Cd metal has been found to cause harmful effects on humans and animals when consuming plants containing Cd (Sidik et al., 2019; Raza et al., 2020). For this reason, in the study, the movement activities of *SIRE1* retrotransposons specific to the soybean plant were examined in callus and leaf samples (in vivo and in vitro) subjected to different concentrations of CdSO₄ stress. Polymorphism ratios between samples were calculated using the Jaccard coefficient. This study is the first report investigating *SIRE1* retrotransposons by *IRAP* (Inter-Retrotransposon-Amplified Polymorphism) marker method in local wheat genotypes grown under heavy metal stress.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material and growth conditions: During the study, Jumhuriyet-100, Kirmizi wheat, and Nurlu-99 wheat genotypes were used. Planting materials were obtained from the Azerbaijan Scientific Research Institute of Agriculture. Samples were taken from both calli and leaves grown under stress and control conditions for 15 and 30 days. Different concentrations of heavy metal (CdSO₄) were applied to the callus and seeds. The molecular part of the study was performed in the tissue culture laboratory of Yıldız Technical University, Faculty of Molecular Biology and Genetics, located in Istanbul, Turkey.

For in vitro callus cell induction, immature embryos cultured in Murashige and Skoog nutrient medium (Murashige et al., 1962) containing 0.8% agar, and 3% sucrose were used. The end of the milk phase was the beginning of the wax phase when the immature embryo was isolated as a primary explant. At this time, the size of the embryo is in the range of 0.8 - 1.5 mm, which is considered the most optimal size for wheat callus induction. Enculturation and subcultivation were performed according to the previously described protocol. (Mammadova et al., 1993). As a callus inducer, 2 mg/l 2,4-D- Dichlorophenoxyacetic (2,4-D) syntenic auxin was added to the nutrient medium. Every 28-30 days, the callus culture was subcultured to a new nutrient medium. After obtaining sufficient biomass during 2 subcultivation periods, the callus culture was transferred to selective factor stress conditions. CdSO₄

concentrations of 10 mg/l and 20 mg/l were used as a selective system.

Molecular analyses

Genomic DNA isolation: Genomic DNA (gDNA) was isolated by taking samples from the control and CdSO₄ stressed variants of callus and leaves of all 3 wheat genotypes (Kidwell and Osborn, 1992). The samples were separated by the CTAB method and the purity of their genomic DNA was measured and diluted in a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (NanoDrop 2000C). Thus, primers were added to the diluted DNA samples and amplified in a PCR device using the *IRAP* marker method. Then, the samples were injected into the electrophoresis device, and the bands were visualized under UV. Experiments were performed with 2 biological replicates.

IRAP-PCR analysis of *SIRE1* retrotransposon and calculation of polymorphism:

For *IRAP-PCR* analysis, the primer with the sequence 5'CAGTTATGCAAGTGGGATCAGCA3' of soybean-specific *SIRE1* retrotransposon was used (Cakmak et al., 2015).

PCR was carried out in 20-mL reaction mixtures containing 2.5 mL of 25 mmol/L MgCl₂, 2.5 mL of nuclease-free dH₂O, 3 mL of 20 ng/ μl template g DNA, 10 mL of 2X Sapphire Amp Fast PCR Master Mix (Takara, RR350A) and 2 mL of primer (10 mmol/L). The amplification conditions were as follows: an initial denaturation step at 95°C for 3 minutes, 95°C for 30 seconds, 50°C for 30 seconds, 72°C for 3 minutes, and 72°C for 10 minutes (T100TM Thermal Cycler, BioRad). PCR products were electrophoresed in 1% agarose gel of 1xTAE buffer at 120 V for 90 minutes. Gel samples obtained from electrophoresis were visualized in a UV transilluminator after washing in 1xTAE solution with ethidium bromide for 180 minutes. Band sizes were analyzed on a 1000 bp (1kb) DNA ladder. Polymorphism values of bands in gel images were calculated by Jaccard Similarity Coefficient (Jaccard, 1908).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In most studies, as a result of Cd accumulation in cereal plants, inter-genotype and intra-genotype changes were observed in them (Ma et al., 2021.). From this point of view, in our analysis, controversial results were obtained between callus and leaf samples of wheat genotypes grown under different conditions, as well as their control samples.

In this study, we identified and analyzed the movements of *SIRE1* retrotransposon specific to the soybean plant in the wheat genome. Based on the results of the research, according to the gel-

electrophoresis results of the control and Cd stressed samples, a total of 150 bands (18 monomorphic, 132 polymorphic) in the range of 750-1750 bp were recorded in the leaf samples (Fig 1). However, no polymorphism was recorded in the callus samples (Fig 2).

TEs have been associated with stress response in most plants, making them a major target of research. However, the high variability, genomic

redundancy, and largely non-coding nature of TEs have made them difficult to study using other methods, either experimentally or computationally.

As can be seen from the table, polymorphism values of *SIRE1* retrotransposon were calculated in wheat genotypes exposed to different concentrations of CdSO₄ (Table). According to the statistical results, the polymorphism rates of 15 and 30-day-old leaf samples varied in the range of 0-20%.

Figure 1. *SIRE1* IRAP PCR results. CdSO₄ stress. Leaf. A) 1-15 (15-day-old), B) 16-30 (30-day-old). M-marker. 1 and 16 Jumhuriyet-100 (control), 2-3 and 17-18 Jumhuriyet-100 (10 mg/l CdSO₄), 4-5 and 19-20 Jumhuriyet-100 (20 mg/l CdSO₄), 6 and 21 Gyrmyzy bughda(control), 7-8 and 22-23 Gyrmyzy bughda(10 mg/l CdSO₄), 9-10 and 24-25 Gyrmyzy bughda(20 mg/l CdSO₄), 11 and 26 Nurlu-99 (control), 12 -13 and 27-28 Nurlu-99 (10 mg/l CdSO₄), 14-15 and 29-30 Nurlu-99 (20 mg/l CdSO₄), NC- negative control.

Figure 2. *SIRE1* IRAP PCR results. CdSO₄ stress. Callus. A) 1-15 (15-day-old). B) 16-30 (30-day-old). M-marker. 1 and 16 Jumhuriyet-100 (control), 2-3 and 17-18 Jumhuriyet-100 (10 mg/l CdSO₄), 4-5 and 19-20 Jumhuriyet-100 (20 mg/l CdSO₄), 6 and 21 Gyrmyzy bughda(control), 7-8 and 22-23 Gyrmyzy bughda(10 mg/l CdSO₄), 9-10 and 24-25 Gyrmyzy bughda(20 mg/l CdSO₄), 11 and 26 Nurlu-99 (control), 12 -13 and 27-28 Nurlu-99 (10 mg/l CdSO₄), 14-15 and 29-30 Nurlu-99 (20 mg/l CdSO₄), NC- negative control.

Table. *SIRE1* retrotransposon polymorphism ratios among groups were calculated with Jaccard's coefficient

%	15-day-old															30-day-old														
	Leaf															Leaf														
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
15-day-old Leaf	1	0																												
	2	20	0																											
	3	20	0	0																										
	4	0	20	20	0																									
	5	20	0	0	20	0																								
	6	0	20	20	0	20	0																							
	7	20	0	0	20	0	20	0																						
	8	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0																					
	9	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0																				
	10	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0																			
	11	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0																		
	12	0	20	20	20	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	0																	
	13	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	0																	
	14	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	20	0																	
	15	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	0	20	0															
30-day-old Leaf	16	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0														
	17	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0													
	18	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0	0												
	19	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0											
	20	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	0										
	21	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0								
	22	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	0							
	23	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	0	0						
	24	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	0	0	0					
	25	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	0	0	0	0				
	26	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	20	20	20	20	20	0				
	27	20	0	0	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	0	0	0	20	0			
	28	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0		
	29	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0		
	30	0	20	20	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	20	20	20	20	20	0	20	0		

Depending on different concentrations of the Cd salt and duration of exposure, different results were obtained on retrotransposon movements. Thus, 0-20% polymorphism was observed in 15-day-old Jumhuriyet-100 leaf samples. Compared to the control, the highest polymorphism ratio (20%) was found in samples stressed with 10 and 20 mg/l Cd salt. These results were repeated in Gyrmzyz bughda and Nurlu-99 wheat varieties. When we pay attention to the general statistical analysis results of the 15-day samples, the retrotransposon movements of all three genotypes were more activated in heavy metal stress than in the control samples.

No polymorphism was detected in Jumhuriyet-100 and Gyrmzyz bughda cultivars on the 30th day of control and stress-applied leaf samples. But despite this, the polymorphism indicators determined on the 15th day of Nurlu-99 and the percentages calculated on the 30th day were the same (20%), that is, the polymorphism rate remained stable.

When comparing the 15 and 30-day-old percentages, polymorphism was calculated in the

range of 0-20% in the Republic-100, Gyrmzyz bughda and Nurlu-99 wheat samples.

The detection of the soybean-specific *SIRE1* retrotransposon in wheat genotypes, a cereal plant, supports the idea that mobile genetic elements, TEs, are transmitted by horizontal transfer (HT). This is evidenced by the discovery of various plant-specific retrotransposons in plants and even other organisms in many research studies. Both retrotransposons specific to barley (0-100%-*Nikita* and 0-67%-*Sukkula*) and were determined by the *IRAP* marker method in the queen bee, worker bee, and larvae by Mercan and colleagues, and high polymorphic values were obtained (Mercan et al., 2022). Interestingly, despite the large number of TEs found in most plant nuclear genomes and the propensity of these elements to move between animal species, no evidence for HT of nuclear-encoded plant transposons has been found. Generally, HT is understood as the process by which genes can move between reproductively isolated species. Not surprisingly, most examples of horizontal transfer of eukaryotic genes involve transposon elements.

Traditionally, HT was considered when highly similar transposon elements were found in distantly related taxa, accompanied by their discontinuous distribution (Diao, 2006).

Thus, summarizing the research work, we can say that the variability of *SIRE1* retrotransposon increased due to the effect of stress, and the determination of soybean-specific retrotransposon in wheat plants supports the idea of horizontal transfer of genes as a result of evolution. The results are expected to provide new insight into understanding the mechanism of abiotic stress and tolerance at the molecular level in the future.

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Effects of Cadmium on SIRE1 Retrotransposon Polymorphism in wheat genome

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Transpozisiya edilə bilən elementlər (TE) bitki genomlarının təkrarlanan ardıcılığını, həmçinin yaranan müxtəlifliyin böyük bir hissəsini təşkil etməklə yanaşı, həyat ağacı boyunca genomların plastikliyi və təkamülünü əks etdirir. Müxtəlif abiotik stres faktorlarının təsiri nəticəsində epigenetik dəyişikliyə gətirib çıxaran retrotranspozonların hərəkət aktivlikləri və onların polimorfizm nisbətlərinin təyini bu tədqiqat işinin əsasını təşkil edir. Bu məqsədlə, tədqiqat işində CdSO₄ stresi tətbiq edilmiş buğda bitkisinin kallus və yarpaq nümunələrində *İRAP* marker metodu ilə soya bitkisinə xas *SİRE1* retrotranspozonu təyin edilmişdir. Kallus nümunələrindən fərqli olaraq, yarpaq nümunələrində 750-1750 bp aralığında zolaqlar müəyyən edilmişdir. Kalluslarda polimorfizm aşkar edilmədiyi halda, yarpaq nümunələrində 0-20%-lik polomorfizm nisbəti hesablanmışdır. Tədqiqatın nəticələrinə əsasən buğda bitkisininə soya bitkisinə xas retrotranspozonların təyini genlərin horizontal yolla transferinin mümkünlüyü ilə izah oluna bilər.

Açar sözlər: *Epigenetika, retrotranspozon, İRAP marker, CdSO₄, kallus, Horizontal transfer*